

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF SYNTAX IN THE ENGLISH
LANGUAGE

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Annotation

Tendency to nominalization: In E. sentence the most important semantic part of a phrase is usually expressed by the nominal part of speech. It is preferable to say 'he gave the coat a thorough shaking' instead of 'he shook the coat thoroughly'. The high frequency of nominal constructions in the predicate makes a supposition that E. is a static language because dynamism is usually expressed through the verbal predicates, which are less popular in E. but nominal predicates sound more idiomatic.

Complex condensation: In modern E. there are complex parts of the syntax consisting of two essential elements. The first one is expressed by a noun or a pronoun (in any case necessary); a non-finite form of a verb expresses the second one.

Key words: Linguistic, Syntax, features, language, predication, representatives, grammatical, stylistic.

Introduction

The combination of these two words is so close that they function as a single part of a sentence, which is called a complex part. If we analyze each member of the complex part separately the sentence meaning will change. Complex parts of a sentence in their information are equal to a clause. But in their form they are more laconic. They make this kind of transition between a complex and simple sentence.

Complex condensation

Complex parts of the sentence are expressed by special constructions in which the relations between the verbal & nominative elements are similar to those between the subject & the predicate. E.g. I insist on John's coming. *John* is a doer & *coming* is an action. I insist that John (subject) should come (predicate). But formally these relations aren't expressed to a full degree. In a sentence the subject is always in a Nominal Case & the verb is in a finite form & it agrees with the subject in person & number.

In complex parts of the sentence the nominal element very often is not in the Nominal case & it doesn't agree with the verb in person & number as the verb isn't in the finite form. That's why the relations between the parts of constructions are called the relations of secondary predication. E.g. I hate (primary predication) you to go away (secondary predication).

Ivanova criticized the theory of substratum & said that the Danish invaders had settled only in the northern parts of the British Isles so the process of reduction & loss of inflections should have taken place only in the northern dialects while actually this process had affected not only the Northern but Midland & Southern dialects as well.

The use of substitution and representation words.

(A peculiar feature of English phrase and sentence)

It is its obligatory structural completeness, e.g. in a sentence the position of two principal parts should be filled and in a phrase a headword should be present, e.g. in Russian it's all right to use one word to answer the question but in standard E. there should be also a verb. In E. to achieve this structural completeness of a sentence or a phrase there are used the procedure of substitution and representation, which are performed with the help of special formal words. Substitution words are subdivided into nominal and verbal, and in case of substitution a formal word stands for one word for one word from the previous context (Your test is better than that of your classmates).

- Nominal substitution words: that, one, it, so (The mother was happy and so was her daughter)

- Verbal substitution words: to do (He ran faster than I did).

Representatives stand for two or more words from the previous context and are also subdivided into nominal and verbal ones. The nominal representatives: the possessive pronouns and the absolute form; the noun in the genitive case (I spent the summer at my aunt's); the pronouns 'some' and 'any' (Can you lend me 30\$? – I don't have any).

Verbal representatives: all the modal verbs, auxiliaries, the particles 'to' and 'not' (Can you give me a lift in your car? – I'd like to but I can't).

These formal words perform a number of important functions in speech:

- Provide structural completeness of a sentence or a phrase;
- Perform a stylistic function because they help to avoid the repetition of one and the same word;

- Textual cohesion (соединение частей текста) Will you come and have dinner with us tonight? – I'd like to.

- The semantic function. It helps to develop the narration further. (She used to be beautiful –But she is today). (Could I come to your party? – Oh, you must).

- Linguistic economy. They reduce utterances and make them more laconic. But the value of information remains unchanged.

The role of context in the defining the grammatical form and meaning of word.

Due to the monosyllabic character of a great number of E. words they do not bear any grammatical information isolated.

The context is playing an important role in defining the morphological nature word and the meaning of poly-semantic words.

Framers use a brand (клеймо) to mark their cattle.

He used to smoke the best brands (марка) of cigar.

He used a brand (факел) to light the road.

Conclusion

Besides being critical to conveying literal sense, syntax is also one of the key tools writers use to express meaning in a variety of different ways. Syntax can help writers:

Produce rhetorical and aesthetic effects. By varying the syntax of their sentences, writers are able to produce different rhetorical and aesthetic effects. How a writer manipulates the syntax of their sentences is an important element of writing style.

Control pace and mood. Manipulating syntax is one of the ways writers control the pace and mood of their prose. For example, the writer Ernest Hemingway is known for his short, declarative sentences, which were well-suited to his terse, clear style of writing. These give his prose a forceful, direct quality.

Create atmosphere. By contrast, Hemingway's fellow story writer and novelist William Faulkner is famous (or infamous) for his meandering, paragraph-long sentences, which often mimic the ruminative thinking of his characters. These sentences, which often ignore the standard rules of punctuation and grammar, help create an atmosphere as much as they convey information.

That said, all writers vary their sentence structure from time to time. Using a variety of sentences is one of the key ways writers engage and maintain their readers' interest.

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